

THE MENTALITY OF PATIENTS AND THE PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS THAT LEAD TO THE APPEARANCE OF CANCER AND THEIR ROLE IN THE THERAPEUTIC CONFRONTATION OF ONCOLOGIC PATIENTS

Emmanuel N Kontomanolis*, Valentin Papamanolis**, Nikolaos Georgiou[△], Sofia Kalagasidou[◇] and Zacharias N Fasoulakis^{***,1}

*Democritus University of Thrace, Greece., **General Hospital of Korinthos, Greece., [△]Stoke Mandeville & Wycombe General Hospital, UK., [◇]Bodosakio General Hospital of Ptolemaida, Greece., ***National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece.

ABSTRACT Aim: This article focuses on the role of psychology with regards to the evolvement of cancer, the psychological effects of cancer and the role of psychology in treating the symptoms of cancer. **Methods:** The available literature in MEDLINE, regarding the role of mentality in the appearance of neoplasia, was searched for related articles from 1978 to 2017 including terms such as mentality, cancer, and adverse outcome. **Results:** Modern medicine was established during the 19th century. Scepticism arose during the 20th century concerning the biomedical model of medicine. That scepticism was caused by the appearance of Psychosomatic Medicine, Behavioral Health, and Behavioral Medicine and recently by Health Psychology. According to traditional medicine, the disease had probably a psychological background but not a psychological cause. Cancer caused misery, but it was not considered to be related to the appearance of cancer. The placebo effect, the so-called psychosomatic diseases, the individual differences on the recovery and the findings on the fragility, make doctors turn to other scientific fields, which could help to the conception and the confrontation of these facts. A relationship between medicine and human sciences such as psychology has appeared. **Conclusion:** Psychology plays a vital role in comprehending both the medical and ethical sides in cancer not only in terms of beliefs and behaviors associated with the onset of cancer (e.g. smoking) but also the psychological consequences, treatment of symptoms, improvement of quality of life, the interval up to the point of the outbreak of the symptoms in disease and longevity.

KEYWORDS medicine; mentality; psychology; patient; neoplasia.

Introduction

Stress is defined as a state of mental or emotional strain caused by adverse circumstances with people suffering from such emotions being trapped within constant and repetitive undesirable mechanisms of reaction such as the avoidance coping behaviour, as a result to the physical and emotional triggers.

At the end of the 20th century, Freud described a situation called "hysterical paralysis", in which patients developed paralysis in their limbs without any organic causes and in such a way that it did not reflect the layout of the neurons. According

Copyright © 2018 by the Bulgarian Association of Young Surgeons
DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.neoplasia-stress

First Received: August 02, 2018

Accepted: September 08, 2018

Associate Editor: Ivan Inkov (BG) Reviewer: Andrzej Margasiński (PL)

¹National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece. Phone: 6972863632 Email: hzaxos@gmail.com

to Freud, that situation depicted the mental state of the person and the expression of repressed experiences and emotions by the form of organic problems, that to date is described as "somatization of anxiety" [1].

Psychology is in reality what regulates our movements and impulses, thoughts and potential in our daily struggle. Galen was the first physician bolstered up the basic role of psychology in cancer and claimed that there is a connection between depression and cancer. In addition to Galen, Erdman in 1701, also supported the fact that cancer may be related to stressful events recognizing the interaction between body and mental state while physical and psychological changes may be not only the consequences of a disease but also their cause [2,3].

Stress and Cancer

It is very common for people who have cancer to deal with psychological problems and stressful thoughts derived both from the uncertainty of the medical situation and the social taboo [4,5]. Many people decide to wait for the end, and such a thought seems to be a relief, a way out for humans to escape from their everyday misery and disappointment while to others, the memory of death might cause a severe depression syndrome since you say goodbye to people you loved and lived with this feeling of sorrow is something temporary and timeless.

The thought that you are departing from a world where you were used to fighting, hoping, caring, socializing and amending within commons is depressive with the resulting emotions being anger and aggression. One of the main reasons stress is being studied and referred to is its potential and catalytic effect in people's social life, profession and well-being. Cancer patients are upset and not happy with their lives; they release their emotions uncontrollably with great power. The idea of being disabled is something that does not coincide with reality; it is too much to bear. Lazarus and Launler expressed the opinion of stress demonstrating a dynamic interaction between individuals and the environment. According to this definition, stress involves interaction between stressful external factors and negative thoughts [6].

Laudenslager et al., presented a study on mice with vulnerability to cancer exposed to stressful conditions (they created stress by shaking their cage). The authors reported that when the stress factor was reduced, there was a decrease in the growth of a tumour. Accordingly, an overload of stress and sadness might lead to a high probability of getting inflammation in any of the anatomical systems of the human body; there is an increasing suspicion that infection may conceal a triggering mechanism in the generation of stress and neoplasia. Given that the stress factor could not be controlled, this would cause an increase in the growth of a neoplastic protuberance [7].

Sklar and Anisman supported that the increase of stress was the cause of an increase in the rate of cancer progression and that anxiety can be deadly regardless of the type of therapy being applied on the patient [8]. Seligman & Visintainer reported the results of a study, where cancer cells were injected in healthy mice that later were exposed to controlled or uncontrolled shocks. The results showed that uncontrolled shocks led to an increase in the tumour's size and that there seems to be a connection between control ability and stress, which may then aggravate the disease [9].

Kiecolt-Glaser et al., support that stress is responsible for the reduction of hormones produced to combat carcinogenesis and rehabilitation of DNA [10]. Two potential mechanisms are

proposed to explain how these psychological factors work to increase cancer risk. The first is by altering the immune and endocrine systems, and the second is via altering behaviours such as sleep, exercise, diet, smoking, alcohol consumption, drug use, and poor adherence to medical regimens, always keeping in mind that besides scientific reports of the pharmaceutical industry role on genetics and neoplasia, life stimuli plays a vital role on carcinogenesis [11]. About the same results are given by the study of Herbert & Cohen, which claim that stressful factors and long-term psychological pressure are linked to the reduction of the immune system's function, that can affect the response to cancer treatment [12,13]. Cortisol, one of the main hormones implicated in cancer development, is a natural hormone that constricts the blood vessels and pushes the bloodstream towards the periphery of the human body (fight and flight reaction), and it is used in as cortisone in deactivation of autoimmune diseases [14]. Other stress hormones also deactivate the immune system, and that is when comorbidities appear. In normal conditions, human cells function and regulate other cellular units under the control of the parasympathetic nervous system. In stressful conditions the sympathetic nervous system takes over. Any negative feeling will immediately trigger the stimulation of the sympathetic system, which in turn will engage in a cascade of "neoplastic" symptoms such as dehydration, acidosis, hypoxia and a lack of the basic nutritional constituents required for a human to be healthy and withstand the psychological and somatic distress [15].

The role of psychology in cancer is seen in some observations like the following one, in which cancer cells exist in most people and are potential to be activated at any moment, but not all people develop cancer while patients with even the same cancer type don't have the same course during their life and only a specific percentage will suffer the most from the disease. It seems therefore that psychology has a specific role to the vulnerability in cancer but also to the progress and possibly to the longevity [16,17]. In the study of Lauren et al., the authors reported an influence of chronic and episodic stress in the annoying symptoms of breast cancer. After diagnosis, stress remained a significant factor in the prediction of the existence of the symptoms and stress seemed to have a slow and accumulative adverse effect in overall survival. The exposure to stressful conditions during childhood possibly increases the sensitivity to the unfavourable effects caused by the exposure in stress as adults, while others support that a large number of stressful factors regardless of time and without the possibility of recovery is harmful to health [18].

Women who survived breast cancer and other gynaecological tumours linked their illness with psychological issues like anxiety, personality, and parameters associated with their everyday lifestyle [19]. Stress also has a negative effect on the behaviours related to health such as diet, physical activity and alcohol use. The non-healthy behaviour of the cancer patient can have significant consequences on his body health [20]. The ways of confrontation also seem important, and if a person has a vulnerability to stress, then the methods he uses to deal with stress may relate to the appearance of cancer.

Personality

In recent years an interest in the connection between personality and cancer has been expressed. Neoplasia alters human behaviour and attitude towards life. The religious idea that your future is predetermined and everything will eventually come

to an end is a stressful thought and knowing that you will face death is not an easy thing to cope with. However, the solution does not always lie in prescriptions. Temoshok claimed that people who develop cancer have a personality often described as passive, calm, desperate, oriented towards others, with no expression of feelings [21]. On the opposite, Eysenk supports that vulnerability to cancer is a characteristic of those who respond to stress feeling despair and distress and those who suppress emotional reactions in life events [22].

Studies evaluating the relevance of psychological factors to carcinogenesis have often examined the role of personality and stress as risk factors in cancer. Nevertheless, all people throughout their lives encounter stressful events and thoughts. If someone keeps an eye on the literature, there are reports of people that have been through severe conditions of anxiety, where daily occupational and family environment are strongly affected. A person does not have to be an expert to realize that it requires huge amounts of personal somatic and psychic reserves to defend oneself against it [11]. The study of Hyphantis et al., showed that defence mechanisms were associated with decisional preferences and interventions in factors which predicted HRQoL (health-related quality of life), in women with breast cancer [23]. In his survey, in which he examined the cognitive functions of cancer, he supports that individuals, characterized as "fighters", are negatively related to anxiety and depression, while fatalism, despair and anxiety related to the decrease of their mood [24].

Improvement in the diagnosis and treatment of cancer as well as in younger ages mean that the percentage of long-term survivors is increasing. They have continuing difficulties with physical and mental health as well as reduced quality of life. Patient's perceptions of the disease affect the results as well [25–27]. It has been reported that younger cancer survivors have greater emotional implications than older women; they have acquired more comprehensive control and comprehension of their disease. Younger patients have been associated with most of the symptoms, anxiety and depression in people who have survived breast cancer, while they have reported more unfulfilled needs comparatively to older women [28,29].

Psychological consequences of cancer

The diagnosis of cancer is an essential psychological stressful factor that can even define the psychological response and the whole patient's defence mechanisms. When the diagnosis is established, the immune system, representative of the defence mechanisms, is being suppressed in a good number of subjects [30,31]. A percentage of 20% may demonstrate major depression, lamentation, lack of control, change in personality, anger and anxiety. The alteration in mentality is sociologically and scientifically more than evident and tempting. Emotional reactions vary from a minor mood disorder reaching up to the highest levels of depression, anxiety and anger. There are cases of extreme hostility. Our lives are simple print-outs of the subconsciousness. It is scientifically stated that 90% of our behaviour comes from the subconscious level; is this the case, some individuals have already decided on their fate, on the path they will during their remaining life [32]. That is what makes feel relieved and devoid of stress. In religion, there are beliefs of an afterlife world, where they now-patients will meet their beloved ones with no fear of losing them again which represents a hopeful and relaxing thought.

Pinder et al. reported that psychological morbidity of patients with advanced stage of cancer was related to the functional situ-

ation and that the malfunctioning state was related to high levels of depression [33]. Taylor in 1983 examined women's' reaction to cancer. The author reported that female patients reacted in three ways. First, they seek for the causes of cancer. Causes included stress, heredity and consumption or contact of carcinogenic substances thought-out their everyday life. Secondly, they were trying to acquire a sense of control over cancer. These control efforts included meditation, positive way of thinking and the belief that the original cause has disappeared. Thirdly, women entered a self-help process by analyzing their situation by comparing it with the condition of other people they knew [34]. The symptom that mainly affects female patients is alopecia caused by chemotherapy. Hair loss is the most obvious adverse effect, and because it often comes in the visual field of the patients, it affects the patient's individuality and attractiveness [35]. Kazuko et al. presented a study where the authors showed that there are six phases through cancer treatment and hair loss. During the first phase, there was an irregular reaction following the doctor's explanation. The same negative reaction occurred during the second phase of hair beginning to fall, during the third phase, when the hair fell intensively, during the fourth phase, when hair fell completely. In the fifth phase, there was a reaction to the behaviour to treat alopecia, and in the sixth phase, there was a reaction in changing the interpersonal relationships [36]. In phase one, when patients learned about the disease and the effects of chemotherapy including alopecia, they felt deep psychological stress. However, they continued to make positive thoughts about life. Although they initially were shocked by the reference to hair loss, they fully understood the necessity of chemotherapy. In phase two, when patients saw their hair fall, they expressed themselves in two ways. The first reaction included lack of agitation and the second reaction included shock and surprise. During phase three, when patients saw their hair falling intensively, their first reaction was composure and disregard to hair loss. Their second reaction was feeling sad about the hair loss. Phase four includes three reactions. The first reaction emphasized the value of life. The second reaction of the patients was the facing of the inevitable reality. The third reaction conciliated a sense of sadness with hair loss. During phase five, patients reacted by wearing a wig or a hat. The first reaction was a positive perception, while in second patients do not accept themselves. During phase six, there are three categories of reactions relevant to interpersonal relationships. In the first case, the patient expresses herself and does not hesitate to talk about her illness. In the second case, the patient does not speak to others, and she wants none to know that she has cancer, except relatives and friends. In the third case, the patient isolates completely, and she does not want anyone to know, except her husband [36].

Patients view cancer as something being altered completely when they live the experience of cancer. Pain is modified by adverse conditions, which are being strengthened by the adverse effect since people with severe and numerous physical symptoms had a more negative image of their illness. A recent systematic review showed that surviving cancer patients may manifest symptoms of anxiety and depression for more than ten years after treatment [37].

Psychological Treatment

Psychology could help a patient's quality of life by relieving the symptoms via psychosocial interventions. One of the fundamental roles of psychology is pain treatment — social support

interventions aimed at reducing denial and strengthening hope. Turk & Rennert encouraged patients with cancer to describe and observe the pain they felt, they encouraged them to develop coping skills, to have positive images, and they taught them some relaxation skills and focused on other things. Most of the patients achieved a reduction of pain through these techniques. Body image counselling helped cancer patients especially after mastectomy to confront lamentation of loss, by providing advice on the differentiated body image [38]. Taylor used cognitive adaptation techniques, aiming at improving patient's self-esteem, their ability to be close to others and to make more sense in their lives. The use of imaging methods has been proven to be particularly useful. In this technique, imagination has been applied to reduce the unpleasant emotional effects of radiation on female subjects suffering from breast cancer. In this research, women that have been through this particular therapy program were divided into three groups. The first group focused on body training with regards to the control of the strength and respiration. The second group used training in relaxation along with spiritual recreations, whereas each was asked to concentrate on a peaceful picture of his own choice. The third group focused upon bringing patients together and engaging in dialogues.

Having taken into account the evaluation results, the authors concluded that women from the first two groups were less distorted compared to women from the control group. Furthermore, female subjects that used the therapeutic recreation processes and relaxation seemed to be more relaxed compared to the group that had focused on body relaxation. It is therefore of vital importance that recreational therapy procedures and techniques should be in detail be comprehended and applied on individuals [34].

Nowadays therapists should be capable of intervening and presenting a broad spectrum of theoretical and practical knowledge; they should be able to apply strategies combined with techniques and counselling to achieve the maximum clinical outcome of their subjects. It should always be kept in mind and guide recreational therapists and psychologists that cure is achieved through sincere interpersonal relationships. The basis of a successful interpersonal relationship is to build on communication among humans. Intermingling and helping people is a very strenuous and complicated procedure, which implies and demands a full understanding of human behaviour. Appropriate psychotherapeutic interventions could modify defence mechanisms. The interventions have been designed to encourage passive patients to become more active [39,40].

A fully supportive part of treating subjects with cancer rests on self-thinking procedures of the individual himself. Since many of the patients will face depression, explaining that a lot of people are going through such diseases with many of them being completely cured needs to be stated. Some might pick up this point by themselves without counselling. It is outrageous for them to realize that their future is changed for good with no chance of finding a U-turn. Logic is recruited to identify the activating event and explain in simple daily terms the above conclusion based on experience.

Conclusion

The critical and indisputable achievements of medical science in both prevention and treatment aim to improve the entire condition of patients, considering health as a particular state of psychosomatic balance. Treatment of health problems from medicine and psychology have brought up some significant and

positive results. Essential factors in the effective treatment of the disease are the quality of patient's life, the recognition of patient's personality in the appearance and the development of the disease, as well as the labelling of the danger factors which relate to patient's behaviour. The contribution of Human Behavior Sciences has been proven to be decisive for the therapeutic effect. The step that medicine should take, to be characterized as "modern", "innovative" and "contemporary", is to overcome the opposition between "body & soul" and the acceptance of the separation between conscious and unconscious.

References

1. Hoehn-Saric R: Anxiety and somatization. *Int Congr Ser* 2006;1287:368–372.
2. HORSTMANSHOFF, H.F J: Galen and his patients; in : *Ancient Medicine in its Socio-Cultural Context*. 1995, pp 83–99.
3. Hankinson RJ: Galen. 2010. DOI: 10.1017/CHOL9780521764407.013
4. National Cancer Institute: Psychological stress and cancer: Questions and answers. *Fact Sheet* 2008;1–4.
5. Krizanova O, Babula P, Pacak K: Stress, catecholaminergic system and cancer. *Stress* 2016;19:419–428.
6. Lazarus RS, Launier R: Stress-Related Transactions between Person and Environment; in: *Perspectives in Interactional Psychology*. 1978, pp 287–327.
7. Laudenslager ML, Ryan SM, Drugan RC, Hyson RL, Maier SF: Coping and immunosuppression: Inescapable but not escapable shock suppresses lymphocyte proliferation. *Science* (80-) 1983;221:568–570.
8. Sklar LS, Anisman H: Stress and cancer. *Psychol Bull* 1981;89:369.
9. Seligman MEP, Visintainer MA: Tumor rejection and early experience of uncontrollable shock in the rat; in: *Affect, conditioning, and cognition: essays on the determinants of behavior*. 1985.
10. Kiecolt-Glaser JK, Glaser R: Psychological Influences on Immunity: Implications for AIDS. *Am Psychol* 1988;43:892–898.
11. Sawada T, Nishiyama T, Kikuchi N, Wang C, Lin Y, Mori M, et al.: The influence of personality and perceived stress on the development of breast cancer: 20-year follow-up of 29,098 Japanese women. *Sci Rep* 2016;6:4–10.
12. Herbert TB, Cohen S: Stress and immunity in humans: A meta-analytic review. *Psychosom Med* 1993;55:364–379.
13. Kruk J: Self-reported psychological stress and the risk of breast cancer: A case-control study. *Stress* 2012;15:162–171.
14. Betterle C, Zanchetta R: *The Autoimmune Diseases*. 2006. DOI: 10.1016/B978-012595961-2/50040-8
15. Goldstein DS: Sympathetic Nervous System; in : *Encyclopedia of Stress*. 2010, pp 697–703.
16. Psychology AR of: Health psychology. *Annu Rev Psychol* 1985;36:349–83.

17. Branney P, Witty K, Eardley I: Psychology, men and cancer. *Psychologist* 2014;27:410–412.
18. Harris LN, Bauer MR, Wiley JF, Hammen C, Krull JL, Crespi CM, et al.: Chronic and episodic stress predict physical symptom bother following breast cancer diagnosis. *J Behav Med* 2017;40:875–885.
19. Zhang N, Fielding R, Soong I, Chan KKK, Tsang J, Lee V, et al.: Illness perceptions among cancer survivors. *Support Care Cancer* 2016;24:1295–1304.
20. Andersen BL, Kiecolt-Glaser JK, Glaser R: A biobehavioral model of cancer stress and disease course. *Am Psychol* 1994;49:389–404.
21. Temoshok L: The relationship of psychosocial factors to prognostic indicators in cutaneous malignant melanoma. *Soc Sci Med* 1985;20:833–840.
22. Eysenck HJ: The prediction of death from cancer by means of personality/stress questionnaire: too good to be true? *Percept Mot Ski* 1990;71:216–218.
23. Hyphantis T, Almyroudi A, Paika V, Degner LF, Carvalho AF, Pavlidis N: Anxiety, depression and defense mechanisms associated with treatment decisional preferences and quality of life in non-metastatic breast cancer: A 1-year prospective study. *Psychooncology* 2013;22:2470–2477.
24. Watson M, Greer S, Rowden L, Gorman C, Robertson B, Bliss JM, et al.: Relationships between emotional control, adjustment to cancer and depression and anxiety in breast cancer patients. *Psychol Med* 1991;21:51–57.
25. Sánchez-Jiménez A, Cantarero-Villanueva I, Delgado-García G, Molina-Barea R, Fernández-Lao C, Galiano-Castillo N, et al.: Physical impairments and quality of life of colorectal cancer survivors: a case-control study. *Eur J Cancer Care (Engl)* 2015;24:642–649.
26. Davis KM, Kelly SP, Luta G, Tomko C, Miller AB, Taylor KL: The association of long-term treatment-related side effects with cancer-specific and general quality of life among prostate cancer survivors. *Urology* 2014;84:300–306.
27. Schmitz KH, Speck RM, Rye SA, DiSipio T, Hayes SC: Prevalence of breast cancer treatment sequelae over 6 years of follow-up: The pulling through study. *Cancer* 2012;118:2217–2225.
28. Kertmen N, Sahin U, Keskin O, Solak M, Petekkaya I, Babacan T, et al.: Comparison of clinicopathological characteristics and outcome of younger and older breast cancer patients. *J BUON* 2012;17:797.
29. Fielding R, Lam WWT, Shun SC, Okuyama T, Lai YH, Wada M, et al.: Attributing Variance in Supportive Care Needs during Cancer: Culture-Service, and Individual Differences, before Clinical Factors. *PLoS One* 2013;8. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0065099
30. FRIED D: Ego Mechanisms of Defense: A Guide for Clinicians and Researchers. *Am J Psychiatry* 1993;150:1116–1117.
31. Sartorius N, Jablensky A, Regier DA, Burke Jr. JD, Hirschfeld RMA: Sources and traditions of classification in psychiatry; in : Sources and traditions of classification in psychiatry. 1990, p xi,-244.
32. Sitzmann T, Bell BS: The dynamic effects of subconscious goal pursuit on resource allocation, task performance, and goal abandonment. *Organ Behav Hum Decis Process* 2017;138:1–14.
33. Pinder KL, Ramirez AJ, Black ME, Richards MA, Gregory WM, Rubens RD: Psychiatric disorder in patients with advanced breast cancer: prevalence and associated factors. *Eur J Cancer* 1993;29A:524–527.
34. Taylor SE: Adjustment to threatening events: A theory of cognitive adaptation. *Am Psychol* 1983;38:1161–1173.
35. Batchelor D: Hair and cancer chemotherapy: consequences and nursing care—a literature study. *Eur J Cancer Care (Engl)* 2001;10:147–63.
36. Ishida K, Ishida J, Kiyoko K: Psychosocial reaction patterns to alopecia in female patients with gynecological cancer undergoing chemotherapy. *Asian Pacific J Cancer Prev* 2015;16:1225–1233.
37. Harrington CB, Hansen JA, Moskowitz M, Todd BL, Feuerstein M: It's Not over When it's Over: Long-Term Symptoms in Cancer Survivors—A Systematic Review. *Int J Psychiatry Med* 2010;40:163–181.
38. Turk DC, Rennert K: Pain and the terminally ill cancer patient: a cognitive-social learning perspective. *Behav Ther Termin care* 1981;95–123.
39. Psychology H: Coping with psychosomatic symptoms: The buffering role of psychological flexibility and impact on quality of life. *J Health Psychol* 2016;1. DOI: 10.1177/1359105316666657.
40. Bond M: Empirical studies of defense style: Relationships with psychopathology and change. *Harv Rev Psychiatry* 2004;12:263–278.